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The Effect of Digital Marketing on Customer Relationships in the Capital of Afghanistan (Kabul)

THESIS

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ABSTRACT

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• The Effects of Digital Marketing on Customer Relationships

Marketers are discovering about using digital channels including the Internet, email, mobile phones, and digital television to cut costs, reach larger and new consumers, customize, interact, and connect with customers better. The ability to leverage digital platforms to develop long-term client relationships and loyalty has recently gotten a lot of attention. We present a model in this article that demonstrates how brand communication, service, customization, and interaction may assist marketers in improving customer relationships.

Digital channels' low prices promote marketers' active and frequent brand communication. This creation of positive customer-brand interactions in a variety of ways. Customers' awareness of marketers' products and services, as well as their participation, may grow. In addition to boosting sales, digital brand communication can encourage good brand attitudes, emotions, and devotion. It is also possible to increase customer activity. Interactivity in digital media provides customers with more alternatives for gathering data, taking action, and receiving assistance. Interactivity also provides new methods to interact with a brand, for as through games or participating in website activities. Personalization can also help customers believe that messaging is more relevant and fascinating.

In comparison to traditional service channels, digital service has the ability to provide clients with more choice, access, control, and convenience. Customers' capacity to actively mold or construct the form of their services improves satisfaction and loyalty. Marketers can also build more personalized services based on the behavior and interests of their clients. Customers can trace their postal packages using the interactive components of digital media, which can be leveraged to provide self-service choices. Customers may be offered additional services such as maintenance reminders and assistance in keeping their products up to date when purchasing products. From a customer relationship standpoint, our methodology assists marketers in better understanding and executing digital marketing and its interactive processes. In addition, a measuring scheme (SARAS) is proposed to track the effects of digital marketing on customer relationships by combining key brand, service, and loyalty measures.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

A. Introduction:

This chapter provides an overview of the research study on the impact of digital marketing on customer relationships, as well as information on the study's background, research goals, research questions, and significance, as well as a discussion of the study's scope.

Digital marketing is a sort of marketing in which products and services are promoted to consumers via digital networks. Platforms are included that do not require the usage of the Internet in addition to online marketing. It offers SMS and MMS phones, as well as social media marketing, banner ads, SEO marketing, and other digital media.

Customers can access information via digital media at any time and from anywhere. Consumers can now trust not just what the company says about its brand, but also what the media, friends, coworkers, and others have to say about it, thanks to the use of digital media.

When a marketer considers the use of digital platforms in marketing from the standpoint of client relationships, there are various advantages. There are many ways to have a conversation with a business, and it may be both persistent and personalized. Learning from and about clients, divulging their requirements and goals, and being able to deliver more personalized service are all advantages. People are also increasingly using self-service in today's highly computerized environment, and they have more options for getting started (e.g., give feedback, check account balances, request and personalize marketing communication).

From the customer's perspective, the perceived advantage of using digital platforms to communicate with a marketer can be expressed in a variety of ways. Money, time, education, convenience, amusement, support, social involvement, status, or anything else the client enjoys could all be factors. Using a digital channel to build a close relationship with a customer can have a significant impact on business success. Analyze was the first company in Afghanistan to use digital marketing in 2008. Since 2012, digital marketing has grown in popularity in Afghanistan.

The purpose of this study is to look at how Afghan marketers may use digital media to enhance and expand their client relationships. Brand loyalty is the most important factor in my technique.

Customer relationship management is seen as the lifeblood of today's company, with advancement and even minor success relying on it. Because the insurance industry's success is based mostly on the services it provides and on continually meeting client demand, a strong CRM program is essential. Customer relationship management (CRM) is a technique for keeping track of a business's contacts with present and potential customers.

As a result of the deployment of new technologies, the advent of digital marketing has resulted in a paradigm shift in global marketplaces and increased consumer purchasing power, resulting in enhanced company competitiveness (Korkpoe & Nyarku, 2013). The fast adoption of digital technology such as smartphones, smart devices, the Internet of Things (IoT), and artificial intelligence (AI) has changed client purchasing patterns and modified future marketing tactics, resulting in the rise of digital marketing. In comparison to traditional or electronic commerce, mobile commerce provides consumers with new value variables that may influence their online purchase intentions (Dastane, Goi, & Rabbanee, 2020).

In comparison to traditional marketing, digital contact offers a new opportunity for social media integration in marketing to lower marketing costs. Marketers, on the other hand, confront new hurdles in determining the best digital marketing mix to reach a large number of prospects, boost brand awareness, and

convert sales through connecting with customers successfully through continuous feedback (Tamrakar, Pyo, & Gruca, 2018).

Furthermore, digital marketing has the ability to attract a diverse set of customers, allowing firms to engage with customers from all walks of life via online media and assist them through the purchasing process (Lodhi & Shoab, 2017). As a consumer interchange of ideas, viewpoints, and experiences, digital marketing effectively boosts buy intent by eliminating brand misunderstandings (Tham et al., 2019). Despite the fact that investing in a digital marketing company demands a considerable financial expenditure, senior management often compares it to traditional marketing channels with a favorable, mature, and proven return on investment (ROI) (Teixeira, Barbosa, & Pinto, 2019). 2016 (Ukowski & Swieczak) Customers can utilize digital marketing as a multi-stream platform to test and review products, influencing the purchasing process.

B. Background of study:

Firms providing services used to focus on market-oriented business, but recent research have indicated that organizations should look forward to developing customer-oriented strategies. Companies compete in this model primarily on the services they provide rather than the main product itself. Despite the fact that this was once the domain of all service organizations, it is now a widespread trend affecting all enterprises. A business that delivers a product or a service primarily to obtain an advantage over its competitors is said to be in service competition. As a result, it is attempting to win a competition based on what it perceives as the business's atom wrapped in a number of other solutions along the atom.

Customers aren't just looking for a good service or a good product; they're also looking for the best way to serve him. A question emerges about how a company can generate a beneficial product, ideal service, or solution. This usually has to do with how a customer feels about a service or product in terms of satisfaction or expectations. In general, the customer's assessment of the complete production, rendering solution, and services on the consuming premises, delivery terms, and co-creation determines the service's quality. The word "relationship" refers to a customer's interaction with a service provider. It is vital to examine how consumer connections are developed in order to attain customer pleasure.

This approach, according to Kaj Storbacka, can be broken down into three pieces. The first step is the prospective customer stage, which concludes when the potential client selects his preferred service provider. In the meantime, the end of this stage heralds the start of the next, the "Customer Relationship Stage." The two sides sustain a sequence of exchanges during the second stage. This is an opportunity for the supplier to put his strategies to work in order to strengthen and develop his client relationship. He refers to the third and final stage as the "Post customer or Lost customer" stage.

C. Problem Statement

This research looks into how digital marketing impacts a company's customer relationship. Digital marketing has been increasingly popular as a means of connecting with customers and brands in recent years. Marketing professionals have always used a variety of venues to provide customer service and advertise goods and services. Digital marketing has aided in the formation of trusting relationships between customers and brands, making it a more relevant medium for increasing brand loyalty.

D. Purpose of the Study

In the past, traditional marketing was the only way to sell a product. We've seen a modern marketing tool called digital marketing emerge in recent years. The way marketing campaigns are implemented has changed. Customers can speak with advertisers directly and provide input. Previously, conversation was one-sided. Other than that, there are a few aspects that have changed. We need to do research to determine the impact of digital marketing on consumer relationships. This research aims to highlight and highlight the effects of digital marketing on customer relationships.

E. Research Questions

The goal of this article is to investigate how digital marketing influences customer relationships. The impacts of communication on loyalty are the main focus of our research.

Finding solutions to specific research questions can help you attain your research goals. The following are the pertinent questions for this study:

RQ1 - How do customers feel about a company's digital marketing efforts?

RQ2 - What type of digital material do consumers expect from a brand?

RQ3 - Which digital marketing platform should a company use to communicate with its customers?

RQ4 - Do customers believe the information shared by the brand on its social media platforms is reliable?

RQ5 – Do brands use social media to spotlight their fans?

RQ6 - How are customers reacting to various sorts of social media posts?

RQ7 - How effective are different brands' contests and efforts at building brand loyalty? RQ8 – In terms of connection development, what distinctions do you notice in digital marketing?

RQ9 – Do you respond to brand content online on a frequent basis and expect a response to your question or feedback?

RQ10-How do you think brands' social media pages compare to traditional communication methods in terms of customer relationships?

F. Hypotheses:

- Hypotheses 1. Brand loyalty is improved by increasing the frequency of brand communication.
- Hypotheses 2. Expected brand communication that is received or accessed when customers want it has a favorable impact on brand loyalty.
- Hypotheses 3. Customers' brand awareness and loyalty grow as a result of activity in virtual brand communities.
- Hypotheses 4. Customers become more loyal to a company if the communications are relevant and intriguing to them.
- Hypotheses 5. The amount of time a customer spends with a brand (online) improves brand loyalty.
- Hypotheses 6. Customers who are engaged and initiate contact (i.e., make product questions, provide feedback, update service profiles, etc.) have a higher level of brand loyalty.

G. Significance of Study:

Customer relationship management (CRM) assists in the search for and connection of clients; CRM maintains all of a client's information; with this information, it is possible to correctly influence a customer, and it can be used to determine which customers will be profitable and which will not. Customers are gathered from a variety of perspectives in customer relationship management frameworks, depending on the type of business they do or their physical location, and assigned to different clients, allowing them to focus and concentrate on each customer individually. The most basic component of customer relationship management is both cost-effective and practical.

When compared to traditional company techniques, the technology used to build a CRM system is also the cheapest and smoothest. These benefits indicate how customers react to different business plans, are automatically classified, and may be accessed from many data storage sites and offices. Computers, the internet, and other online technologies have ushered in a flurry of change and simplification in today's modern society, when everything happens in the blink of an eye. The system directory will be able to provide unique linkage data to a corporation that wants to look at an individual client and how he is tied to them.

Client relationship management, or CRM, would show a successful run between the business and the technology utilized therein if the company has good up-to-date information about the customer. Data containing client information would make it easier for the company to deal with difficulties, maintain better and faster connections, and minimize time wasted searching through multiple directories. Call routing, load

balancing, and call distribution, among other modern technologies, would cut the time spent performing services across the network. Important data is safely consolidated in customer relationship management, and it can be accessed at any moment with only a click. The length of time is reduced by several orders of magnitude, while efficiency is increased by orders of magnitude.

H. Scheme of the study:

The first chapter provides an overview of the overall value and purpose of studies, as well as the most important aspects of how to conduct and organize research.

The second chapter is devoted to a review of the literature.

The research in the second chapter focuses on conceptual topics such as overall digital marketing, customer relationship which have been discussed in earlier articles, books, and articles published in recent years.

The methodology chapter is offered in this article to demonstrate the type of methodology employed for today's dissertation. Methods, information, and resources are discussed in this study.

Chapter four, Analysis and Findings, assesses the research findings in order to answer the study's questions. The SPSS application is used to read the data, and the results are presented in the form of tables and graphs.

Conclusions and Recommendations (Chapter 5):

Finally, the conclusion and recommendations of studies are shown in the final chapter. At the end of the project, this item, designated Appendix I and Appendix II, has a list of resources and a questionnaire.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Introduction

The contemporary model of CRM, or customer relationship management, is established and drawn from QM (Quality Management) theory and innovation employing cutting-edge technology. In the way customer relationship management is viewed, there is no obvious consistency. However, as with any other definition, a solemn conclusion may be drawn after comparing all of the theorizers' agreed-upon elements to be given as a basic concept, namely, "customer relationships management" refers to marketing strategy, client retention, and overall customer management. Differences in purchasing power, purchasing traits, and consumer preferences led to the creation of customer relationship management. However, if all customers were the same, there would be no need for extensive customer relationship management. As a result, corporations are already developing schemes and scenarios for various types of consumer groups in order to maximize profitability. Dastane, O. (2020).

It is easier to provide assistance and services to clients who are classified more precisely and exhaustively, allowing firms to quickly target their products or services to the right individuals with the necessary resources. Because of the increasingly difficult and tight market environment created by saturation and complex competitions, customer relationship management is gaining prominence these days. If a business wants to compete, it must understand CRM and perform extensive customer research. S. Alavi, Ph.D. (2016).

Customer relationship management (CRM) is a business-focused global program that aims to build a presence across all company divisions. CRM involves product testing, human resource, billing, product assembly, product manufacturing, customer purchasing, product engineering, product marketing, general sales, and other factors, in addition to how a corporation or firm delivers customer care. CRM (customer relationship management) is a multi-faceted tool for thoroughly searching customer data. Data is gathered from a range of client views, helping the company to have a better understanding of the customer. The business would be better able to respond to current customer preferences, target the correct audience, and predict future desires. S. Oré Calixto, Oré Calixto, Oré Calixto, Oré Cal (2021).

Some theorizers characterize customer relationship management as "an all-encompassing approach that seamlessly integrates sales, customer service, marketing, field support, and other customer-facing operations." Customer relationship management is also considered as a strategy for a business to keep its most profitable customers while reducing costs and boosting contact volume, which draws more interest. Theorists have proposed a variety of definitions and academic debates on CRM, while practitioners have proposed a variety of practical prescriptions for resolving issues and putting them into practice. S. Oré Calixto, Oré Calixto, Oré Calixto, Oré Cal (2021).

Many firms consider customer relationship management to be a technology solution. CRM is a technology solution that improves targeting efficiency in some firms by taking into account individual databases, sales department automation technologies, as well as sales and marketing duties. Businesses see CRM as a technology designed exclusively for one-on-one customer engagement, whether it's for sales, call center, or marketing. Two-way communication has greatly improved as a result of technological improvements, notably on the Internet. Customer relationship management (CRM) is defined as the integration of enterprise-wide technologies that work together, such as a phone support system, website, data warehouse, accounting, sales, marketing, and production. O. Dastane, O. Dastane, O. Dastane, O (2020).

Without adequate marketing material to motivate clients for future sales and a cycle of recurrent sales, converting sales leads to sales is difficult (Epstein & Yuthas, 2007). The customer relationship was harmed, if not jeopardized, when Yahoo's 500 million user account data was leaked (Whitler & Farris, 2017).

Information security and privacy are critical, and customers should be given control of their data before it is exploited through pop-ups. However, these have become a barrier in digital marketing because customer data is exchanged without consent between organizations, and customers should be given control of their data before it is exploited through pop-ups (Bostanshirin, 2014).

Customers are growing increasingly skeptical of digital marketing, so organizations should emphasize brand trust and excellent branding as answers. Despite this, many businesses are investing in digital marketing in order to stay afloat now and in the future. False digital marketing adoption by businesses is costly, time-consuming, and unsuccessful in the business world, as Malaysia currently lacks digital marketing competencies (Gaur, 2019). A customer's purchase intent is influenced by their online search and the amount of time they spend on e-commerce websites (Donni, Dastane, Haba, & Selvaraj, 2018). Understanding how digital marketing affects purchase intent can help e-commerce organizations attract both new and repeat visitors to their websites. S. Alavi, Ph.D. (2016).

CRM developed from today's complicated and competitive modern enterprises, which combine sophisticated customer experience with quick technical improvements to boost consumers' purchasing power, according to Wong, Dastane, Satar, Safie, and Ma'Arif (Putney & Puney, 2013). Furthermore, the traditional CRM method—now symbolized by the use of digital marketing to interact, advertise, and help customers with more advanced technologies—remains loyal and gratifying (Nykamp, 2012). The CRM deployment allows for more data mining in the library pool, which makes smart marketing material easier to understand and access for clients while also lowering the expenses of ineffective marketing methods (Stueart & Moran, 2007).

Rehmani and Khan (2011) investigated the impact of e-media on purchase intent and developed a model for mobile phone purchases. De Pelsmacker, Van Tilburg, and Holthof conducted a similar study on hotel reservations (2018). It has been investigated the impact of social media on purchase intent, as well as the mediating effect of consumer views (Lim, Radzol, Cheah, & Wong, 2017). Several research on the history of purchasing intent have been undertaken (Kooli, Mansour, & Utama, 2014; Verhagen & Van Dolen, 2009). The importance of digital marketing has been established in numerous evaluation studies on purchase intent (Ezgi & Nasir, 2015). The present literature on online purchase intent, on the other hand, does not adequately capture the impact of digital marketing on buy intent. S. Oré Calixto, 2015.

In customer relationship management, information technology is utilized to collect data, which is subsequently disseminated so that a more personalized path of engagement with the client can be developed. In addition, the firm provides a progressive analysis and amplification process to help clients maximize the value of their work with organizations. Customer relationship management (CRM) is a technical solution that allows companies to create a cross-functional, customer-oriented organizational process management strategy that improves interactions. Dastane, O. Da (2020).

Because of the numerous tech-based choices for automating customer relationship management that are accessible on the market, it is frequently not well-constructed as a meaningful set of technical breakthroughs. However, the bulk of businesses are only now discovering the strategic importance of customer relationship management, which is transitioning from a tech-based to a value-based activity. The use of information technology as a sparkplug in a customer relationship management approach lights the ignition to boost the profitability of client engagements. S. Oré Calixto, Oré Calixto, Oré Calixto, Oré Cal (2021).

Innovations and improvements in technology, combined with a highly competitive marketing interface and a widely used internet, have proven to be today's and tomorrow's client profitability engines, capable of enabling it in the best possible way and proportionate to the company's resources to every active part that affects the customer relationship. In order to accomplish transactions, customer relationship management

can provide clients with convenience, simplicity, and personalization. In this situation, the type of interaction that is taking place is irrelevant. S. Alavi, Ph.D. (2016).

In today's environment, businesses have realized the importance of how customer relationship management can aid in the fight against competition and the opportunities that exist therein. This feature of modern business became apparent once businesses recognized the necessity for a global competitive environment. Businesses cannot compete just by replicating products or services and offering the smallest advantages. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) allows a platform to transcend beyond modest levels of interest while focusing on building real-world relationships with its customers. Businesses that focus on providing tailored products and services for their customers will be able to withstand today's fierce competition and thrive tomorrow as industry leaders. Dastane, O. (2020).

First and first, CRM must be defined. Customer relationship management (CRM) is a method of tracking a company's interactions with current and potential customers. CRM has a favorable impact on customer satisfaction behavior and knowledge when banks, particularly in the service industry, exchange customer-related information with their supply chain partners. CRM is essentially a method or set of actions for gathering and delivering data that aids a bank's strategic decision-making. Through individualization and customisation, CRM systems assist businesses in increasing the profitability of their contacts. Claes Fornell, Sunil Mithas, and M. S. Krishnan (Sunil Mithas, M. S. Krishnan, and Claes Fornell, 2005).

CRM has emerged as one of the most dynamic technology topics of the millennium, with applications in a wide range of businesses, including banks, hospitals, telecoms, electricity providers, and internet service providers. CRM isn't a new concept, but it's become more important as a result of recent technical improvements and innovations in information and corporate software. (Popovich and Chen, 2003; Popovich and Chen, 2003; Popovich and Chen, 2003).

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a structured system for influencing customer acquisition, loyalty, retention, and profitability through strategic connections that comprehend how to smooth client behavior. From a strategic standpoint, a treated Customer Relationship Management integrated framework, or a method that provides client-specific service in the hopes of sustaining a long-term relationship and bringing out current client desires. CRM was examined from both a social control and a technological standpoint in the research. New technological, institutional, and foreign elements have all been shown to have an impact on customer relationship management implementation. Hasanat, W. M., Hoqueb, A., & Hamid, A. B. A. (2019). We'll go over the following titles in greater detail:

B. Technological factor

It is widely acknowledged that technology has characteristics that influence compliance decisions and how they are implemented. The decision-making process, human ingenuity, compliance rate, and perceived qualities were all identified as issues related to innovation. Furthermore, the adoption of the perceived attribute's theory to assess IT innovation based on the five characteristics of innovation, such as relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, observability, and reliability, has been heavily reliant on perceived attribute's theory. This presentation has added to the discussion by looking at the effects of technical attributes on an institutional level. As considered from a different perspective, customer relationship management (CRM) is "one-to-one" marketing that employs 12 personal computer technologies such as information, interaction technologies, and mass production to develop and maintain training interlock between customers and enterprises. Businesses have been able to give services and commodities that each client requires based on personalization by assessing customer reaction criteria, interactive data, and history-based deals data. Dastane, O. Da (2020).

C. Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is a relatively new technique in the field of online marketing that entails influencing customers through a variety of interaction channels, such as social media, mobile apps, blogs, emails, and even search engine optimizers (SEOs), in order to achieve closer communication in various forms that deliver advertising to customers (Garca, Lizcano, Ramos, & Matos, 2019).

Digital marketing, according to Sawicki (2016), is an exploration of the huge digital universe of technology that has established a platform for connecting a large number of prospective audiences. Furthermore, digital marketing entails the promotion of goods and services using an e-commerce platform that reacts in real time to an Internet connection.

It includes outlets that do not require the use of the Internet in addition to online marketing. It offers SMS and MMS phones, as well as social media marketing, banner advertising, SEO marketing, and a variety of other online services. Customers can get information at any time and from any location they want thanks to digital media. Consumers can now trust not just what the firm says about its brand, but also what the media, friends, peers, and others have to say about it, thanks to the use of digital media. S. Alavi, Ph.D. (2016).

A marketer could benefit from looking at the use of digital channels in marketing via the lens of client connections. Learning from and about clients, divulging specific requests and interests, and being able to provide better personalised service are just a few of the advantages. Customers can now receive up-to-date information, compare products and services, and interact with marketers more easily thanks to the internet.

In today's highly digitized world, clients are increasingly adopting self-service, and they have more alternatives for how to get started (e.g., give feedback, check account balances, request and personalize marketing communication). From the customer's perspective, the perceived value of communicating with a marketer via digital channels can be stated in a variety of ways. Money, time, information, convenience, amusement, support, social interaction, status, or anything else the client loves could all play a role.

Analyzen began digital marketing in Bangladesh in 2008. Since 2012, digital marketing has grown in popularity in Bangladesh. The purpose of this study is to look at how Bangladeshi marketers may use digital platforms to develop and increase their client relationships. Brand loyalty will be the most important factor in my framework. O. Dastane, O. Da (2020).

Integrated marketing services that use the internet to attract, engage, and convert customers are referred to as "digital marketing." Content marketing, influencer marketing, SEO, social media, and online advertising are examples of digital marketing platforms that allow businesses to engage with customers and track the effectiveness of marketing initiatives in real time. Actor Lee Oden is well-known (Lee Oden, 2014).

The term "digital marketing" refers to a variety of activities. It combines all marketing strategies with the use of digital gadgets (i.e. online, on mobile and on-screen). Take a look at some of the most popular digital marketing methods today: Using e-mail to market your business: It is one of the earliest forms of digital marketing, and it comprises sending tailored or targeted messages at the appropriate times. (2015, KVRwebtech) The most common sort of digital marketing is search engine optimization, which tries to improve a website's presence in search engines. Some of the tactics employed in this process include on-site technical evaluation and enhancement, blogging, link-building, and content production. S. Alavi, Ph.D. (2016).

The price is determined by the level of competition for the keyword you're bidding on. Social Media Usage: Managing a brand's image across several social networks such as Twitter, Facebook, Pinterest, and others is what social media is all about. Over the last few years, this kind has grown in popularity, maturity, and complexity. (2015, KVRwebtech) Combining online with pay-per-click advertising is not a good idea! This refers to the practice of placing advertisements on other people's websites. You may, for example, purchase ad space on a popular website and pay the website's owner. (2015, KVRwebtech) Communication via text: It is the most extensively utilized Digital marketing type, in addition to the aforementioned online marketing components. People's reliance on smartphones for quick and timely information has grown exponentially as smartphone adoption has surged around the world. (KVRwebtech, 2015).

D. Customer Relationship Management

CRM has evolved into a three-dimensional structure with collaborative, operational, and analytical capabilities, and it has become a key tool in the development of cost-effective corporate strategies for a variety of customer evaluations (Buttle, 2006). CRM goes beyond modern tools to analyse customer data, retain existing customers, and develop new customers through a successful strategy execution process in order to build an effective communication life cycle. The consumer is loyal to the supplier and purchases from them again and again because they have built a deep emotional bond with them. For a consumer, the feeling could be intensely personal, with the customer preferring and trusting in the company's ability to successfully address their concerns and problems (Amofah& Ijaz, 2005).

Customer loyalty is a long-term advantage for the organization, according to Abu-Alhaija, Yusof, Haslinda, and Jaharuddin (2018), who want to make their groups competitive by using a comprehensive CRM system. Positive experiences and values encourage customers to spend impulsively because their relationship with the company grows steadily with increasing levels of customer satisfaction; digital technologies enable businesses to implement effective communication strategies and pay constant attention to customer satisfaction. S. Alavi, Ph.D. (2016).

According to a study by Akhmedov (2017), an efficient CRM approach encourages customers to provide favorable reviews, respond less to competitor marketing, and forgive the company for providing erroneous information; it also fosters high levels of loyalty and contentment. Previous research has looked at purchasing intent extensively in order to better understand the impact of a variety of factors on online shopping intent (Gan, 2017). However, little study has been done on the influence of digital marketing and CRM on purchase intent. The goal of this research is to look into the role of CRM in mediating the relationship between digital marketing and purchase intent in order to bridge the information gap. Digital marketing is the most current marketing approach for communicating and promoting products and services regardless of time, location, or cost limits (Kim & Ko, 2012).

According to Wibisurya (2018), digital marketing has a favorable impact on purchase intent, as well as compelling content, personalization, and customisation for consumers. Poyurak and Softic (2019) revealed that digital marketing has a favorable effect on purchase intentions through a consumer exchange of thoughts. Nonetheless, based on the architectural arrangement of digital marketing, Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019) observed no significant association between digital marketing and purchase intention. Through the use of digital marketing methods, such an action does not enhance buy intents (Liat&Wuan, 2014).

Digital marketing has progressed at a dizzying pace, necessitating significant changes in strategies and technologies. Guerreiro and Loureiro (2020) investigate how different social network users interact and disseminate information about the causes of the digital age (the expansion of Information and Communication Technologies), as well as how people seek out marketing campaigns tailored to their tastes and preferences.

According to Viana (2020), services are evolving as corporations seek more analytical and technological information. These new standards are linked to the integration of social media data into CRM platforms, which will help to improve customer data. Hasanat, Has (2019).

According to Dastane, CRM is described as a method of learning and influencing consumer behavior through the use of meaningful communications in developed American and European countries (2020). CRM is defined as a strategy for acquiring new clients and retaining existing ones in developed American and European countries, according to Dastane (2020). CRM, in fact, ensures both client loyalty and revenue for businesses. Despite the fact that digital advertising investment has been steadily increasing since 2013, most organizations in Peru do not use it, as evidenced by the fact that only 34.5 percent invest in it in 2017, despite the fact that it has been steadily increasing since 2013, he is not a major figure in management (2018).

Social media and digital marketing materials, according to Drew et al. (2017), have an impact on the social, economic, and environmental complexity of the quinoa sectors in Peru and Bolivia. According to Fong (2019), the sector has adjusted to the changing needs of the Peruvian market by providing digital solutions that provide quick information, convenience, and modernism when purchasing a new product or service. On the other hand, more than half of Peru's SMEs (micro and small businesses) are in risk of going out of business due to a lack of clients as a result of their failure to embrace recently established digital technologies. Small businesses find it harder to attract new customers as a result, resulting in low sales. S. Knox and L. Ryals (2001).

This state educational institution, which has been in operation for more than 55 years and has a population of 560 students, saw a growth of 670 secondary level students until 2015, and then a 16.4 percent decrease in the student body population to 560 students by 2019, representing a 16.4 percent decrease in the student body population. Because poor customer service, abuse of digital media, and a preference for competition may have contributed to the significant drop in students, it was suggested that the chosen Digital Marketing tactics be investigated to see if they had an impact on client relationship management (CRM). O. Dastane, O. Da (2020).

It's a type of digital marketing that uses the Internet and social media apps (like Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and Twitter) to target specific audiences with commercial messages delivered to their smartphones, tablets, and computers. It is distinguished by message personalisation and interaction, as well as the ability to broadcast product information using specialized techniques and in volumes much exceeding traditional media's capacity (Amson, and Kent, 2021).

Digital marketing, according to Del Toro (2020), is "the use of digital technology to support and facilitate marketing efforts." Its use, in general, increases the profitability of product and service purchases by increasing client acquisition. As a result, digital technology and the development of a strategic approach are gaining steam, allowing businesses to better understand their customers' interests, preferences, and products (presentation, quality, quantity) in order to meet their needs. Its implementation facilitates national and international trade processes in which various techniques are used to develop business models and strategies aimed at detecting opportunities in global markets, necessitating the establishment of communication channels as well as the incorporation of a marketing strategy. According to digital marketing gurus, if a product or service can't be found on the Internet, it doesn't exist (Bricio Samaniego et al., 2018).

E. Content marketing

Material marketing is a type of digital content marketing that focuses on producing, disseminating, and sharing valuable and high-quality content (Kotler et al., 2017). It's a method of grabbing the attention of customers through high-quality content, but from a position of optimization. Its correct distribution and advertising assist us not only in earning industry reputation, but also in achieving our goal of generating qualified traffic to our assets (Velázquez-Cornejo & Hernández-Gracia, 2011).

F. Social media market

Social media marketing, according to Cortado and Chalmeta (2016), is a form of social interaction, or spaces of connectivity and coexistence. The dynamic interactions between the users who incorporate them define them. Social networks are horizontal, open systems that connect people who share common interests and concerns. As a result, they have evolved into a social structure that enables a group of people to pool resources and solve problems. According to Kumar et al. (2016), it is a low-cost communication strategy that allows businesses to extract value from current and potential customers while also allowing brands and customers to interact in novel ways. Dastane, O. Da (2020).

G. Customer relationship management (CRM)

CRM is crucial to the company's goal and senior management's CRM strategy for its employees, according to Alqershi, Mokhtar, and Abas (2020). CRM (customer relationship management) is a business approach that focuses on analyzing and influencing customer behavior through effective interactions in order to increase customer acquisition, retention, loyalty, and profitability. For the CRM process to succeed in accomplishing goals and enhancing the firm's performance, this interaction between the company and its employees is also essential. Customer happiness and retention, as well as employee satisfaction and, as a result, business performance, can all benefit from a successful CRM deployment.

CRM potentials also reflect the skills and procedures required for sustaining, building, and enhancing meaningful relationships, and research has linked CRM to company performance. Deductively, businesses should design a CRM system that meets their goals while utilizing existing resources. CRM approaches that are properly implemented create opportunities for service providers, resulting in customer satisfaction (Salem: 2010).

From low commitment and emotional link to high commitment and emotional bond, consumer relationships span the spectrum. Transactional consumers are customers who shop around. They employ a complete decision-making process in which they gather data from which they build and assess options in order to choose the best product. They actively encourage and seek out competing information, and they do not limit the scope of their investigation. Repeat customers are referred to as loyal customers by many practitioners since they buy from the same store on a regular basis while also being open to new offers. For the purpose of convenience and cost savings, people trust the store to fulfill their purchasing goal, and they make fewer judgments.

When seasonal sales or discounts are offered, a customer who is loyal to Wal-Mart because of his or her faith in the company's ability to provide low prices may simply switch to another company. Consumers who have created an emotional or social bond with a brand/retailer have made a non-contractual commitment to them are known as relational consumers. Most relationship customers make purchasing decisions without gathering intelligence to generate alternatives, which slows down the process. They don't even glance at competitor advertisements, implying that they are unaware of competitive information (Cahill, 1998).

Consumers place a different value on long-term partnerships. Firms must utilize transactional or relational marketing techniques that are suited to their clients' desires (Jackson, 1985). Transactional customers have a poor relationship orientation and place a higher value on short-term benefits. Customers who are repeat or loyal to a certain marketer are aware of the benefits of familiarity, such as decreased transaction costs and loyalty program rewards.

They have a connection orientation that is mild. Relational customers place a high value on long-term connections and cooperation. They prefer to work with B2C companies because they want to minimize both their options and their risk (Sheth and Parvatiyar, 1995). Depending on their relationship orientation, consumers will place a different value on their overall pleasure or their trust and commitment to marketers (Garbarino and Johnson, 1999). Total satisfaction is the key mediating construct between component

attitudes and future intentions for low-relationship customers, according to studies. L. Ryals and S. Knox (2001).

For the high relational client, trust and commitment, rather than satisfaction, are the mediators between component attitudes and future intention (Garbarino and Johnson, 1999). Customers who have had a pleasant transactional experience with a retailer are more likely to return. Customers return because they receive favorable feedback and tangible rewards. A positive review could be based on the conviction or confidence that the shop sells appropriate goods. Relational customers return because of their commitment. Because of their affections for each other, they may overlook minor shortcomings (Cahill, 1998).

A thorough comprehension of one's spouse is required for relationship development. Furthermore, the psychological benefits of doing business outweigh the financial benefits (Gwinner et al., 1998). Transactional customers are less aware of marketing than repeat customers, who are more informed and have distinct preferences. Customers that have a strong relationship with a company have a high level of marketer expertise, which can lead to emotional connection. Not only does physical exertion imply involvement, but it also implies emotional commitment. Consumer initiative refers to a person's level of involvement in a market. Both are essential in the formation of relationships.

Transactional clients are uninterested in marketing campaigns and serve as passive targets. Although repeat customers are increasingly involved with marketing activities, they remain primarily passive targets. Active, participating partners, not passive prey, are the characteristics of relational consumers. The relationships that repeat customers form are typically transactional in nature (Iacobucci and Ostrom, 1996). Relational customer connections are characterized by noncontractual commitment. While relationship consumers are regular buyers, they have a high and consistent "share of wallet" when it comes to repeat purchases. While long-term benefits are important to relational consumers, short-term benefits are particularly appealing to repeat customers. Mustaphi, B. M. (2020).

Mass marketing or transactional marketing tactics work better for transactional customers. Marketers rarely acquire much personal information other from the information required to complete transactions. Segmentation, loyalty programs (Dowling and Uncles, 1997), and a mix of transactional and relationship marketing strategies benefit repeat customers (Pels, Coviello, and Brodie, 2000). Purchases are influenced by both material and social rewards.

Because they want long-term relationships, relationship clients should use RM. Customers are eager to share more personal information in order to keep the relationship going and benefit from it. Marketers are more inclined to emphasize intangible consumer benefits such as risk reduction and the development of emotional/social interactions. The first thing a marketer must examine when building an RM strategy is if the relational client group is available or viable to create. Relational customer groups are rare and difficult to form in the traditional consumer market due to the market environment, type of offers, and limited communication methods. The Internet, on the other hand, has had a big impact on the consumer market and is aiding RM in general. O. Dastane, O. Dastane, O. Dastane, O (2020).

H. The Impacts of the Internet on the Consumer Market

Throughout history, the development and application of new technology, particularly communication technologies, has enabled the establishment and implementation of successful marketing plans. A number of researchers have looked into the role of technology in RM. One of the four types of customer service resources identified by Gronroos (1996) is technology. Zineldin (2002) even said that RM is ineffectual without sufficient technological implementation. The Web can be considered as a wonderful approach to deploy RM in the consumer market because it is an interactive medium.

The Internet has been positioned as a new marketing tool or a new market (Wang et al., 2002). The Internet is a medium through which retailers and customers may communicate with one another. This effective communication tool is necessary for sustaining a regular, continuous, and frequent exchange of information, which is a prerequisite for building connections. Retailers can implement RM methods at a reasonable cost by using the Internet. However, the Web's ramifications go beyond its utility as a communication tool. It becomes a part of the market and has an impact on certain areas of the market. As a result of the Internet, retailers, industry structure, type of offerings, and consumers are all changing. Taken collectively, these developments make the retail environment more suitable for RM deployment. The Web can be regarded both a sustaining and disruptive technology in terms of consumer RM (Christensen, 1997).

I. Facilitating RM in a broad sense

The Internet is a tool that allows businesses and customers to communicate with one another. This efficient communication tool is required to maintain a regular, continuous, and frequent transmission of information, which is necessary for the development of connections. Retailers can implement RM procedures at a reasonable cost by using the Internet. The consequences of the Web, on the other hand, go beyond its utility as a communication tool. It integrates into the market and has an impact on certain market segments. As a result of the Internet, retailers, industry structure, type of offerings, and consumers are all changing. When these characteristics are combined, the retail environment becomes more favorable. In terms of consumer RM, the Web can be considered both a sustaining and disruptive technology (Christensen, 1997).

Consumers can interact more with advertisements thanks to the Internet. Enabled interactivities are essentially computer interactions in which the user is in command. Internet encounters with salespeople, in most cases, lack personal interaction. Service automation is plausible because to the technical aspect of the engagement, which could reduce the density of individual encounters while increasing the total degree of interaction received by the general public. The usage of additional media can help individual relationships, such as those in technical support. Consumers may contact marketers more frequently as a result of the widespread availability and ease of use of Web engagement. The Web also allows consumers to communicate with other consumers who share similar interests through virtual communities. A. Stojiljkovi (2019).

In a broad sense, the facilitation of the Web to RM aims to improve customer satisfaction at every stage of the shopping/decision-making process. Consumers can access more marketing material, product options, and make smarter decisions thanks to the advantages of the Internet. A buyer who wants to buy a product, such as a camera, but has no prior understanding of the subject can benefit from the Internet. Previously, this buyer would go to a camera store and rely exclusively on the recommendations of the salesman. You may discover a list of camera manufacturers, as well as full features and pricing lists, on the internet. In addition, the consumer can receive feedback from other users to aid in their evaluation of the options.

This is a fact that has been recognised by all corporate organizations. E commerce has long been regarded as the future's sales engine. Further complications arise from recognizing and understanding the necessity to evolve an E Business strategy. The first and most crucial task for businesses is to organize their financial priorities. Capital and cash flow are the backbone and requirement of today's operating businesses. Simultaneously, massive sums of money must be set aside on a monthly basis to guide the company through the E Business strategy, which is a future requirement. M. Saarela, and L. Isohella) (2017).

The commitment of the organization's senior and middle management is the second hurdle to E Business implementation and transformation. The E Business transition must be owned by functional and administrative management, who must be actively involved throughout the implementation process. Managers, on the other hand, are frequently confronted with the realities of pursuing targets and devoting time and effort to daily transformation initiatives.

Is there enough excitement and dedication on their behalf to lead the program's implementation? E implementation programs are designed in such a way that they must be owned and implemented by the functional owners, and they cannot be completed by a third party independently. Of course, outside consultants will be called in to help with the project, but the final mile execution will be handled by operational workers on the ground, therefore the functional managers will be the owners. Isohella, L. (2017).

There could be a host of issues with the organization. On the other hand, the E implementation plan must include all of the elements and build the most successful strategy possible. If top management is committed and in charge of the entire process, it is possible to do so successfully. Take, for example, Hewlett Packard. In order to create synergy, HP's management decided to purchase Compaq and merge the two companies. Of course, there were certain similarities in terms of items and so forth. The manufacturing and supply chain processes used by both organizations, on the other hand, were vastly different. HP decided to merge the Blue HP and Red Compaq product lines, as well as implement SAP throughout the platform. Blue line sold a variety of products, including printers and consumables that were made to order. Red Line primarily produced PCs for the SOHO market on a build-to-order basis. Market segmentation and supply chain activities are separate for both product lines. In order to provide inventory visibility down to the last mile, HP needed to connect both supply chains and warehouses. A. Stojiljkovi (2019).

In most nations, the implementation was done in stages. HP chose not to enable all SAP R/3 components. For inventory and warehouse operations, they elected to link to a third-party service provider's WMS system. SAP got a message when products were automatically received at a warehouse, allowing the system to drop orders against the inventory received. The local WMS system took care of the rest of the distribution and delivery tracking.

The final Proof of Despatch was uploaded to HP's website, where the end user could view it. For thorough implementation at the country level and throughout all warehouses in the country, large investments in both hardware and software, as well as a significant amount of time, were required. The project was able to maintain its focus, support, and resources for the most of its sixteen-month lifespan thanks to a well-organized project process that included senior management involvement on a global level as well as regional and country level sponsors.

The road to success was paved by top management's commitment to build and operate the system, as well as great project planning and execution skills. HP benefited from the project in many ways, including leaner resources, faster and more flexible processes, inventory and order visibility, shorter procurement, manufacturing, and delivery lead times, lower production costs, and a significant reduction in logistics costs associated with higher volumes. T. Nikunen, M. Saarela, E. L. Oikarinen, M. Muhos, and L. Isohella (2017).

Increased customer awareness, the ability to handle enormous numbers of client demands, and the development of customer connections are just a few of the well-known benefits of a successful implementation program. Your website's IT partners or Web Developers provide you with a wide range of reports and data on a variety of aspects.

As a Marketing Manager, you must be familiar with the E business program and be able to obtain information from it if you want to transform your website into a powerful sales engine. The website gives you an up-close, real-time picture of your market and clientele. Unlike traditional channels, where your customers are at a distance and distant, you can see your customers' activity up close and nearly instantly. Your consumers could be an individual, an organization, the government, the military, or a dealer, entire seller, retailer, or a mix of all of these. A. Stojiljkovi (2019).

The lifespan of products and services is quite short. It's also crucial to consider the buyer's loyalty and purchase habits. When making strategic decisions regarding your products, markets, and pricing in a continuously changing and complex environment, it's easier to make decisions based on facts and data than

than previous records, performance, and field sales employee understanding. Second, gaining understanding about your customer can provide you with insights into market trends.

Attempting to establish and maintain a relationship with your customer is an essential element of your job. Customers today are extremely demanding and well-informed. To maintain a relationship with an existing consumer, you must continue to provide value to them. You can clearly identify the segments to which your customers belong, as well as their expectations and behaviors. Understanding your customers' expectations will make it easier for you to offer a personalized value proposition for each unique customer, enhancing the customer's experience with you. Apart from gaining a better understanding of your customers and their demands, you can also acquire useful insights that can help you improve your supply chain processes. Distinct clients have different purchasing techniques and methods. A defense or manufacturing organization may use the E Bid strategy to purchase products, whereas traders and retailers may want to put weekly online orders or buy more based on the discount slab available. Another big customer might want to go with JIT supply and expect to issue JIT orders via email. Understanding customer expectations and delivery requirements can help you keep stocks low, reduce distribution locations, and use more efficient delivery methods. Overall, the more time you spend analyzing and learning from the E reports and data you generate, the better off your operations will be. (Christensen, 1997).

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method utilized in a research project is critical. I need to identify each phase, evaluate the concept, and conduct the research. The research design is included, which is the foundation of any investigation. It is impossible to get at the correct study aspect without this. It's a strategy for driving research forward in the appropriate direction. It gives me the opportunity to respond to the first question in my problem description. It allows me to respond to a logical question and determine the elements I'll need to begin the initial research, such as whether the study will be qualitative or quantitative, sample size, and descriptive or explanatory research. It all boils down to selecting on the appropriate method for conducting the research. I'll carry out the data collection procedure and analyze the outcomes. Following data collection, analysis is crucial since it will give me with the study's final result, which will be based on the information I have obtained.

A. Research Design

Each researcher must adhere to a predetermined design framework in order to conduct quality research. Exploratory, descriptive, and causal research are the three categories of predefined research designs.

Exploratory Research: This type of study is done to identify a solution to an issue that has yet to be identified. It helps you choose the optimal study plan, data gathering method, and subjects.

The primary goal of descriptive research is to have a better understanding of the research issue. The researcher is trying to come up with a fresh approach to a problem that already exists. In other words, the researcher delves further into the subject in order to provide a thorough account of the issue.

Causal Study: This type of quantitative research is also known as descriptive quantitative research.

My research is primarily descriptive. The study's main purpose is to determine how digital marketing influences consumer interactions. Both quantitative and qualitative data were analyzed in this study.

B. Data Collection

I recruited a random sample of 25 people from the general population to conduct my research. My choice was chosen completely at random. Anyone who can use the internet, is active on social networking sites, and has a basic understanding of digital marketing is included in my sample. The majority of the people in my sample are university students, with the exception of a few professionals. Because the material I've obtained is unique to my research, I'm using primary data. I'll use computer-assisted data collection to gather my information.

Information that is quantitative: It is used to represent quantitative data numerically. The information is supported by specific figures and facts. Numbers are used to describe the degrees of association between the many factors studied and historical data. The numerical data values are simple to understand and can be represented with common charts and diagrams. Quantitative research generally yields accurate results (Gates, 2005). Quantitative data makes it easier to draw conclusions. It responds to numerical input. A tiny change in numerical data might cause a cascade of problems.

Qualitative data is information that is descriptive in character. Rather than figures, the study relies on descriptions and more detailed information. This type of data is used to express degrees and state facts in words. It's tough to capture or assess data that isn't mathematical or quantifiable. To obtain greater results, the data cannot simply be linked together (Langer, 2006). A researcher could misinterpret qualitative data.

I will use both quantitative and qualitative data in this study, but predominantly quantitative data.

C. Data Reliability and Validity

The extent to which results are consistent over time and provide an accurate picture of the total population under inquiry is referred to as dependability, and a research instrument is deemed trustworthy if the results of a study can be duplicated using comparable techniques. (Joppe and colleagues, 2000).

Validity determines if the research accurately measures what it was supposed to measure or if the research conclusions are correct. In other words, can you use the research tool to hit "the bull's eye" of the study object? Validity is usually determined by asking a series of questions and then seeking for answers in other people's research. (Joppe and colleagues, 2000).

D. Research Limitations

Time restrictions and restricted resources are the most difficult aspects of conducting research. I couldn't get more than 25 people to fill out the survey. Furthermore, I was unable to access a number of past research studies conducted by other academics. I worked with a lot of clients, but I wasn't able to provide much inside information that would have made this study more credible.

CHAPTER FOUR

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion

From the previous data, we can determine that customer relationship management has a strong positive link with related variables (in here, client satisfaction). This isn't to say that every factor has a big impact on the variables that are related. Customer satisfaction has been shown to be aided by how employees act as well as social network connections.

The findings of our investigation are consistent with those of earlier investigations. According to the outcomes of our study, staff who can build a positive relationship with clients can keep them satisfied. Customer loyalty is heavily influenced by employee behavior. The organization must prioritize the two pillars of employee conduct and relationship building. Employees are required to be not only pleasant and kind to their customers, but also to have sufficient product knowledge and communication skills to establish relationships with them. They must also sustain client satisfaction through great employee behavior. Employees must be taught how to respond quickly to client requests. They must also be able to show concern and care for their customers. No business, whether retail or otherwise, will be able to exist without excellent customer relationship management. Clients who have mastered courteous expressions and personal connections sorts of sociality are pretty satisfied with professional service rendering, according to our findings. Furthermore, regardless of the sort of service provided, clients prefer service providers who are pleasant and professional, according to the study. "Courtesy expressions" are used at the start and end of the encounter, as well as a way to demonstrate a stronger connection with the client.

Customer relationship management (CRM) is a cross-functional, customer-focused approach enabled by technology and applied through business processes. Customer relationship management necessitates a shift in both the institution's overall structure and how clients are communicated with. The extent to which an organization obtains and uses easily available customer data to design and implement plans to satisfy client demands in the client's best interests is referred to as client orientation.

CRM is defined as the alignment of corporate operations with client strategy. Maintaining a company-wide commitment to CRM necessitates constant education and training, as well as the adaption of performance criteria toward customer orientation.

B. Limitations and recommendations for future studies

The following recommendations are what we consider to be helpful:

- **Culture of the Organization**
Commercial faithfulness is seen as critical to the success and megahit of customer relationship management. A fundamental shift in company culture requires strong leadership, commitment to customer relationship management, and backing from senior management. The senior management board must update its goal for providing value to clients and communicate that vision to their employees at all times.
- **Making use of new technology**
The last ten years have been marked by rapid development and innovation. New technologies appeared more regularly, causing market stability to be disrupted. Customers have become more mobile, aware, and demanding as a result of technological advancements. Competitors, however, got increasingly adept at quickly enhancing their operations.
- **Customer service/representative investment** Personalized attention, face-to-face human contact, welcoming customers, smiling, presenting a fresh and appealing appearance to customers, and engagement are all significant factors that contribute to increased CRM.

As mentioned in the proposal, a few things may come to light that should be reviewed on a quarterly and/or semiannual basis to ensure that the clients are getting what they want.

C. Recommendations for managers

This study was conducted to determine the effect of digital marketing on customer relationship, and it was limited to Kabul due to a lack of resources and time; therefore, it is recommended that the researchers conduct it in other provinces of Afghanistan where similar programs are in place for more information and results.

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